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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

El uso del teléfono celular en la atención psicológica de estudiantes Universitarios /DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7812174

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Resumen

El teléfono ha ganado popularidad entre las personas, particularmente entre los niños a nivel mundial. Las oficinas de bienestar han surgido como resultado de nuevas innovaciones. La disponibilidad de servicios de salud mental ha aumentado como resultado de la proliferación de dispositivos y aplicaciones móviles. En todo el mundo, el uso de teléfonos móviles está aumentando rápidamente. El número de usuarios de teléfono indica la ocurrencia de una transformación de correspondencia. El uso excesivo tiene efectos morales y sociales positivos y negativos. El uso inapropiado de los celulares y sus accesorios genera graves perjuicios y problemas sociales. Este estudio examina el ejemplo del uso de teléfonos móviles y su relación con la provincia psicológica y cercana a casa de los estudiantes universitarios de Teherán, teniendo en cuenta la rapidez de los acontecimientos y el uso extensivo de teléfonos móviles y su programación excepcional en todos los campos. Cincuenta y cinco estudiantes masculinos y femeninos de las facultades de ciencias de Teherán fueron seleccionados al azar para esta inequívoca revisión correlacional transversal. La encuesta de bienestar emocional aplicada sirvió como herramienta de selección en este estudio. Se utilizó SPSS para examinar los datos. Los resultados generales demuestran que la media y la desviación estándar del bienestar mental están significativamente relacionadas. Las personas que solo usaban sus teléfonos durante cortos períodos de tiempo hacían menos llamadas, enviaban menos mensajes instantáneos y tenían una mejor salud mental.

Palabras clave: uso de teléfonos celulares, confianza, bienestar psicológico, estudiantes, bienestar mental

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The use of cell phones in the psychological care of university students

Abstract

The phone has gained popularity among family members, particularly among children everywhere. Well-being offices have emerged as a result of new innovations. The availability of mental health services has increased as a result of the proliferation of mobile devices and applications worldwide. Worldwide, the use of cell phones is rapidly increasing. The number of phone users indicates the occurrence of a correspondence transformation. Over-the-top use has positive and negative moral and social effects. The inappropriate use of cell phones and their accessories causes serious harm and social issues. This study examines the example of using cell phones and their relationship with the psychological and close-to-home province of Tehran College students, taking into account the swiftness of events and the extensive use of cell phones and their exceptional programming in all fields. Fifty five male and female students from Tehran science colleges were randomly selected for this unmistakable cross-sectional correlational review. The meeting emotional well-being poll served as the selection tool in this study. SPSS was used to examine the data. The general results demonstrate that the mean and standard deviation of mental well-being is significantly linked. People who only used their phones for short periods of time made fewer calls, sent fewer instant messages, and had better mental health.

Keywords: Cell phone use design, confidence, psychological wellness, Tehran College understudies, electronic wellbeing

1.- Introduction

In the cutting edge time, simple and far reaching admittance to the Web and remote innovation is an indication of mechanical advancement. In the present period, it is sufficient to contact a companion who is miles from you with a call or an instant message at the most reduced cost and in the briefest conceivable time. Today, cell phones are viewed as the main innovation which makes individual security. It has made an individual's social relationship significant in an organization. Cell phone highlights have made different interactive media abilities and limits, for example, sound recording, video recording, photography, web, and satellite association, and similarity with PCs and their projects. E-wellbeing and organization advances and their application in medical care have prompted the arrangement of Wellbeing. Email is an effective method for giving information and care abilities to the overall population, admittance to great quality consideration paying little heed to general setting, getting a good deal on counteraction therapy and recovery of patients, and diminish hanging tight time for clinical benefits. Analytic and revealing of side effects and indications of the infection which has showed

up. In an innovation situated climate, electronic psychological well-being care is the main point. Electronic emotional well-being is the arrangement of emotional wellness administrations through innovation and the Web. Different advances are restrictions in giving psychological well-being care administrations. It makes and gives a reasonable foundation to the production of dynamic themes in the treatment cycle. The four areas of self-show of electronic mental polls are the arrangement of control and appraisal data, mediation, and social help. One of the limits made in this field is to give data in the field of ID of crews, treatment, and preparing required in this field. Along these lines, doing interventions is simple. Poise and self-assessment of close to home and the ability to understand anyone on a profound level by the client in genuine circumstances are something featured in this field. Local area support in online tests remembers bunch conversation for discussion channels and the utilization of informal communities for this issue. One of the benefits of electronic self-evaluation is the chance of being mysterious in the pursuit with the goal that you can involve it for certain reasons. New advances give simple preparation to clients. You are remembered for the innovation situated program to easily introduce your inquiries. Web based psychotherapy is a short informing program for local area backing of clients for the counteraction, treatment, and recuperation of mental problems. Dealing with your inquiries alongside Care Wellbeing Portable is one of the center regions in the Wellbeing study. E-Wellbeing is the strengthening of individuals needing clinical therapy and the cooperation of individuals in charge, distinguishing proof of side effects, therapy, and giving individual criticism and clinical help. With the extension and advancement of the utilization of keen cell phones, it is anticipated that constantly 2030, the utilization of cell phones as the primary instrument for utilizing different administrations will increment, and accordingly, cell phones are currently one of the apparatuses for giving wellbeing administrations. In such manner, Application Versatile applications genuinely deserve consideration. Portable applications are programs that are intended for electronic gadgets, for example, cell phones and tablets. The main purposes of the cell phone application are giving psycho-instructive substance, restraint, strengthening care, and strengthening. Different examinations have shown that the utilization of versatile applications in giving psychological wellness administrations has impacted a large number of issues like melancholy and tension, despondency, bipolar, uneasiness, and psychosis. The aftereffects of the examination have shown that patients with maniacal issues, will generally utilize the savvy portable application for controlling their mental issues. Applications intended for cell phones set out a freedom for treatment in the wake of holding gatherings (Mohamadi, 2005).

2.- Research Background

As one of the methods for correspondence, the phone has stood out for everybody for exceptional reasons like accessibility and inexpensiveness (Abdullah, 2004). Preparation of the phone started during the 1960s in the Scandinavian nations, and toward the finish of that very decade, the main phone was utilized. This innovation was delivered to the market in 1975 and the primary cell phone network was sent off (Geser,

2006). From that point onward, the original of cell phones was utilized in 1979 for business purposes in America and Japan. Afterward, this framework was updated and the second era of computerized cell phones entered the market, which is some of the time called portable and once in a while cell phones in certain nations (Rosenberg, 1965). The quantity of cell phone supporters overall expanded from 12.4 million out of 1990 to 500 million out of 2000, and this pattern go on until this year, which is 2022, and today practically all individuals in each general public have a brilliant cell. Today, the cell phone isn't just a method for correspondence between clients, however it has different purposes, for example, getting to the Web, sending and getting SMS, photographs, and films, overseeing data, overseeing individual data and data terminals and diversion bases, and so on. Somewhat recently, the cell phone has opened its place among individuals, particularly youngsters on the planet. Taking into account the many purposes of this method for correspondence, like saving time and working on the personal satisfaction. Notwithstanding, its negative angles can't be overlooked. So the absence of ideal and right utilization of cell phones has caused serious social and social harm in the public arena, and its coordination with the existences of teens and youngsters has created issues that should be overseen and controlled. Many schools reported the restriction on the utilization of cell phones for understudies quite some time ago, yet many schools all over the planet have not had the option to forestall this. 45% of young people, particularly in enormous urban areas, utilize cell phones. Furthermore, this can be a danger to the event of irregularities. Likewise, as indicated by the directed exploration, 30% of youngsters utilize cell phones as a toy and one more 70% use them for discussion with companions and diversion (Lee, 1996). As per the consequences of the exploration, this specialized device makes an unsettling influence in the educating and learning of individuals. The utilization of cell phones in schools is restricted to games and diversion, paying attention to music, and taking pictures, schools actually miss the mark on limit with regards to the logical utilization of this specialized apparatus. As per review and examinations, the utilization of cell phones in schools, as other data and correspondence innovation items enjoys benefits and disservices, and this issue is touchier for the age gathering of youngsters and teens. Since they are in the states of schooling, development, and character improvement, their weakness to the irregularities in the public eye is more than different gatherings. Perpetrating wrongdoings in teens and youngsters is connected with the utilization of cell phones, so the exorbitant utilization of cell phones is more among the people who have various types of deviations like medication and liquor utilization. Non-understudy cell phone proprietors have more fitting ways of behaving than understudies (Rice, 2003). The aftereffects of studies show that understudies with low emotional wellness and low fearlessness invest the greater part of their energy utilizing cell phones. Additionally, the discoveries of the examinations show that young people who utilize cell phones are all the more mentally powerless (Joiner, 1999).

Materials and methods

Taking into account the rising utilization of cell phones and considering the high measurements of this age bunch in Iran, it is important to lead research on this age bunch. The motivation behind this study is to decide the example of cell phone use and its relationship with the mental condition of understudies at Tehran colleges. This examination was completed with the universally useful of deciding the example of utilizing cell phones and its relationship with the psychological condition of understudies at Tehran college with the unique goals of analyzing the example of involving cell phones in the psychological condition of understudies and furthermore deciding the connection between the example of utilizing cell phones and the psychological condition of understudies. The speculation of this exploration was that there is a connection between the example of utilizing cell phones and the psychological condition of understudies. The sort of elucidating study was a relationship. The factual populace concentrated on in this examination were male and female understudies of Tehran College. 55 individuals were chosen from this college by arbitrary examining technique. The testing technique for this irregular review was basic in this manner that the rundown of two classes of 55 understudies in the graduate degree in brain science was taken from the training office of the schools and the classes were chosen two by two and the analyst visited the classes and directed the meeting surveys among the understudies. Classes were conveyed. The information assortment instrument was utilized from the meeting psychological wellness survey with 17 inquiries. The general score of every individual is acquired from the amount of the scores of the two subscales. Subsequent to finishing the polls, the information were investigated utilizing SPSS factual programming.

3.- Interview questions

The interview questions for the first part were as follows.

Table 1.

Interview questions: Section one

1	What is the status of marriage and celibacy of students?
2	How much is the family's income?
3	How long have you been using a mobile phone?
4	Who pays for your cell phone?
5	How many messages do you send during the day?
6	How many phone calls do you make per day?
7	Do you prefer voice call or video call?
8	Why do you use SMS?
9	What is the purpose of telephone communication for you?
10	When do you send messages?
11	What is the content of your messages most often?

12	When do you silence or turn off your phone?
13	Is the mental state of students different before and after using mobile phones?
14	Is the mental state of students different?
15	Does the use of mobile phones affect the psychological state of university students?
16	How many minutes do you talk on your mobile during the day?
17	Does having a mobile phone affect students' self-esteem or not?

Source: Authors development

4.- Data Collection

The consequences of the segment information of the exploration tests show that the greater part of the college understudies were female and most of the understudies were single. The family pay of most of understudies was 10 to 15 million Tomans each month and all understudies had shrewd cell phones. As to span of utilizing cell phones, a large portion of the understudies have been involving cell phones for quite a long time or more. The consequences of the meeting showed that there was a huge contrast among young ladies and young men, and young ladies utilized cell phones for a more drawn out timeframe. Concerning installment of telephone charges by people, the consequences of the test showed a massive distinction among male and female understudies, and female understudies paid more. As to address, do you send a few telephone messages during the day? The outcomes showed that there is a measurable contrast among young ladies and young men and young ladies send 20 additional messages during the day. As to number of calls during the day, young ladies had a bigger number of calls than young men. With respect to address, do you favor communicating something specific or a voice call? Most female understudies favored voice calls, while most male understudies favored video calls. As to respond to the inquiry, for what reason do you favor sending names? The most well-known answer was connected with lower cost. Concerning issue of phone correspondence, the female understudies responded to questions connected with companions and requested news from family. The outcomes showed a tremendous contrast. Concerning season of sending superfluous messages, the most widely recognized answer is the point at which I need. As to content of the sent and got messages, the reaction of the understudies was welcoming, and the outcomes showed a tremendous contrast among young ladies and young men. As far as downtime or hushing the cell phone, the greater part of the responses were connected with the time it is fundamental. As to kind of telephone, the majority of the understudies utilized iPhone and Samsung telephones. The accompanying outcomes were acquired with respect to the fundamental reason for the examination, which was the psychological condition of understudies utilizing cell phones. With respect to address, is the psychological condition of understudies unique? The one-way examination of the change test showed a huge distinction that hostility in understudies was more subsequent to utilizing cell phones. With respect to connection between the strategy for use and mental state and its pointers in the college, the Pearson relationship coefficient showed a critical

outcome in regards to nervousness and sleep deprivation. As to particular reason for the exploration to decide the connection between the approach to utilizing cell phones and the mental condition of college understudies, the inquiry is whether it meaningfully affects the mental condition of college understudies. One-way investigation of difference was utilized to address this inquiry. The outcomes showed that the length of having a cell phone didn't essentially affect the psychological condition of college understudies, and that implies that all understudies of this college didn't have an alternate mental state with various terms of having a cell phone, or as such, the span of having a cell phone significantly affected their psychological state. It has not. Concerning next question, how long do you chat on your cell during the day, the test shows a huge outcome. The normal for both young men and young ladies shows that understudies who utilize their cells for under 30 minutes have higher psychological wellness. As far as the quantity of everyday messages, the outcomes were huge. The typical in two colleges shows that understudies who send under 20 messages are intellectually better. Beheshti understudies who favor messaging contrasted with voice calls have gotten huge outcomes. The issue of phone correspondence shows huge outcomes The hour of sending pointless messages had critical outcomes. Likewise, there were critical outcomes in the field of two inquiries, the substance of the messages and when the cell phone was switched off or quiet. The outcomes with respect to different inquiries were not critical. How long have you had a cell phone? Does it influence the confidence of college understudies? One-way investigation of change was utilized to respond to this inquiry. The outcomes show that the span of having a cell phone affected understudies' confidence. What's more, with respect to the following inquiry, who pays for your cell phone? Is it connected with the confidence of understudies of three colleges? One-way investigation of fluctuation was utilized to address this inquiry. The results were not significant.

Figure 1.

The first to third priority of students to use mobile phones

Figure 2.

The type of phone used by students

5.- Results

The outcomes have shown that most college understudies have claimed cell phones for quite a long time or more. In comparable examinations, the greater part of the understudies had cell phones when they entered the college. This study shows that most of college understudies' telephone costs were paid by their families. Inordinate utilization of PDAs and calls might adversely affect the monetary status of people and families, a few guardians are compelled to burn through a lot of cash month to month on their and their kids' mobile phone costs. The outcomes show that college understudies talk for something like 5-10 minutes for each call, and the most time was connected with female college understudies who had over 30 minutes of discussion during the day. An enormous number of understudies expressed that on the off chance that they didn't have a cell phone, they would live more effectively and without stresses and that involving the telephone for quite a while would make them be all the more intellectually occupied. The consequences of a similar report likewise show that students invest a typical measure of energy on cell phones. The examination results show that all understudies use informing more. The aftereffects of the examination show that the first to third need of understudies is voice calls, instant messages, and telephone peripherals, separately. Likewise, the outcomes show that all understudies use voice calls and female college understudies do this more. At the point when individuals arrive at the age of 20, they are more intrigued by voice calls than SMS. Likewise, different sorts of exploration show that the utilization of voice calls is more than SMS. The outcomes show that college understudies favor sending messages in examination with voice calls, and the explanation is connected with the minimal expense of SMS. Every one of the understudies referenced the issue of correspondence in any case, getting news from companions and afterward reaching family members and family. The more innovation is utilized, the more correspondence with companions is contrasted with family. In a review, 64% of young ladies and 47% of young men named correspondence with family as the main justification behind feeling the requirement for a cell phone, and 18% of young ladies and 33% of young men felt the requirement for a cell phone to speak with companions. The exploration results show that correspondence with family among young ladies and young men has diminished by 3% and 8%, separately, and correspondence with companions has expanded by over 6% and 11%, individually. The aftereffects of the current exploration show that most of understudies have referenced that they switch off or quiet their telephones when they need to be aware. It is important to make

reference to that they didn't focus on the responses in class and public gatherings. As per measurements in 2022, Apple and Samsung brand telephones were the top rated organizations in Iran. With respect to number of times changing the telephone, the outcomes show a huge relationship in the college. Specialists express that youngster's lean toward new models of telephones and frequently have purchasing the most up to date telephone as a primary concern. With respect to speculation of the exploration, there is a connection between the approach to utilizing cell phones and the emotional wellness of understudies. The consequences of the test show that there is a connection between the approach to utilizing the telephone, psychological well-being, and confidence. The consequences of the exploration likewise showed that there is a positive and critical connection between the elements of the overall wellbeing of understudies and how much cell phone use. With regards to the connection between the span of cell phone use and the psychological condition of understudies, the outcomes show that understudies who utilize the telephone less and send less messages have higher confidence. Researchers have tracked down in examinations that high utilization of cell phones, with extroversion and trust, is related with low breath. The consequences of this examination likewise show that individuals have higher psychological well-being the less time elapses since they have a cell phone. Hence, it tends to be reasoned that having a cell phone for quite a while makes them utilize the telephone more and as it were, the telephone turns into a substitute for their gatherings with loved ones, and subsequently, the absence of up close and personal correspondence causes a reduction in their psychological wellness. In the field of psychological wellness and the approach to utilizing the telephone, the general outcomes demonstrate that the people who utilize the telephone for a more limited timeframe. During the day, they settle on less decisions and send less instant messages, and have higher psychological well-being. With respect to approach to involving the telephone and its psychological state in the college, the Pearson connection showed huge outcomes in regards to uneasiness and a sleeping disorder. The examination results showed that there is a critical connection between understudies' tension and how much utilization of cell phones. That is, with the expansion in the utilization of cell phones, the level of understudies' nervousness likewise increments. Likewise, the test showed huge outcomes in the field of wretchedness and the approach to utilizing the telephone. Specialists express that individuals who utilize their telephones a ton have more indications of sorrow. Despondency as a typical peculiarity in teen's increments with over the top utilization of mechanical devices. As a rule, wellbeing objections like weariness, stress, tension, and rest problems are more normal in understudies who routinely utilize cell phones than in the people who use them less. As to measure of cell phone use and its relationship with confidence, the consequences of the investigation of change showed that the term of having a cell phone meaningfully affected the confidence of college understudies. This implies that confidence won't change with various degrees of telephone use. Maybe the explanation is that the understudies who utilize the telephone indeed because of the absence of time and exercises connected with their investigations have disregarded their loved ones and think about the telephone as a reasonable substitute for meeting individuals, and this point has taken out their concerns. As a general rule, taking a gander at the historical

backdrop of examination and the physical and mental impacts of involving cell phones in the public eye, the need of exploration for destructive cases is important. Without a doubt, these days, innovation, particularly cell phones, has impacted different parts of individuals' lives.

6.- Conclusion

Today, the cell phone has a strong situation as one of the signs of new correspondence innovation in the individual and public activity of an individual. The impact of cell phone applications in life is a worldwide peculiarity in our general public. In any case, it has arrived at such a degree that the serious and key weaknesses of this advanced innovation have become obvious. Weaknesses in different social, social, conduct, mental, clinical, legitimate, and Discipline manage injury. As indicated by the outcomes acquired from this review, it is recommended to utilize radio, TV, and different media to acquaint understudies with the benefits and burdens of cell phones, as well as correspondence administration focus workplaces and cell phone deals workplaces, instructive bundles in view of the problems brought about by the utilization Destructive to circulate among purchasers, which can prompt the extension of the right culture of utilizing this telephone. The consequences of this examination can likewise be utilized in understudy advising focuses and it is important for guides to address advisors' ways to deal with diminishing the unnecessary utilization of cell phones.

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